

S I N G L E

D5.1 Methodology framework

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Executive summary

In the present public document, we share the methodology framework for data acquisition that will be followed by SINGLE partners.

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1. Introduction

The SINGLE project aims to demonstrate the competitive advantages in terms of efficiency, flexibility of integration, reduced costs, and low environmental footprint of Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Reactors (PCERs) for Ammonia Dehydrogenation (ADH) producing directly high purity pressurized hydrogen by implementing a novel stack design integrated in a module for 10 kg H₂/day operation and evaluating the value stream for scale up economics for future large-scale deployment.

One of the focuses of the project will be developing life cycle models. LCA and LCCs rely heavily on data, and the quality of the results mostly depends on both the architecture of the model and the quality of the data that is fed to it. Looking at the methodology for data acquisition and processing is therefore vital to ensure that the results obtained are representative of the reality of the technology.

2. Goal and scope

The objective of this document is to define a methodology to acquire, and mainly process, the needed data for the life cycle models that will be developed throughout the project. This methodology will encompass the definition and assessment of the different data sources that are available, setting up a classification and documentation system to ensure transparency and traceability throughout the different stages of model development.

A data evaluation methodology is therefore described to standardize data collection and classification in SINGLE. The methodology intends to provide a clear procedure to analyze a given dataset with the objective of assessing its quality and reliability. This procedure will paint a clearer picture of the usefulness of a given dataset, aiding partners in the decision of what data is good enough to be used in the models.

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3. Data collection strategy

Both the LCA and LCC analysis will use data to assess the different parameters in the life cycle analysis of the SINGLE technology. The output results that these models provide are heavily dependent on the input data, so ensuring that correct and reliable data is used is paramount to obtaining good results.

Data collection is a vital part of LCA and LCC modelling, often being one of the limiting factors to the development of these models. To ensure that reliable data is used, a strategy must be defined to streamline the process of data acquisition. The data acquisition process must be standardized and transparent, ensuring that the results are backed by reliable datasets.

To ensure that the data quality and reliability objectives are met, a methodology must be defined so the different SINGLE partners follow the same process during the data acquisition phases of their respective tasks. This methodology must be backed by a set of templates to aid in the standardization and classification of the datasets.

The data acquisition process will first start with the assessment of the source that provides the dataset that is of interest to the researcher. Depending on the source type, different procedures will be followed, with the aim of assessing the organization that is behind the collection of data.

Once the source has been cleared, the next step will consist in documenting all of the different characteristics that defined the dataset. This process will mainly entail filling up a standardized template where all of the relevant parameters for the next steps of the process will appear. This will both aid in defining the usefulness of the data and in classifying its quality.

The next step will consist in reviewing the overall quality of the data, by following a procedure based in international standards with the aim of solidifying the reliability of the datasets used in the model, and consequently ensuring that the results meet all of the necessary standards.

Finally, once all of the previous steps have been completed, an assessment of the nomenclature can be made. Doing it previously can lead to wasted time since the dataset may be discarded during the collection process. So, the partner must ensure that the dataset uses the correct nomenclature before it is stored/used.

To better illustrate the data acquisition methodology, a flow diagram of the process is presented:

Figure 1. Data collection framework

4. Data source evaluation

Classifying and reviewing the source that produces the datasets that will be used in SINGLE models is a vital step to ensure reliable results are obtained. Understanding the processes followed to obtain data is key when evaluating the different data sources since it allows the researcher to make a good assessment of the reliability of the data that he/she intends to use.

Sources can be broadly classified in two categories, primary and secondary data. Depending on what category is assigned to a dataset, a different review process will be applied.

4.2 Primary data sources

The main source of reliable data, and one of the main objectives of the SINGLE project, is the operation of a pilot plant to evaluate the performance of the reactors on which the project is based. The module of these reactors will contain an array of different sensors, which will be complemented by the ones of the pilot plant to achieve a primary source dataset.

This dataset will be complemented by internal data provided by the different partners of the SINGLE project, aiding in the reliability of the models and the quality of the results. So, primary sources are cleared to advance to the next steps of the data acquisition methodology.

4.3 Secondary data sources

Although a lot of high-quality data can be obtained from a pilot plant, there are several parameters for which it is not feasible to obtain data from a primary source, so drawing from generic data sources is inevitable.

To ensure good quality results, the SINGLE researchers tasked with developing these models will have to evaluate the sources from where they'll draw data. Only secondary data from verified and recognized sources must be used. To make an initial evaluation of these sources, a transparency review is proposed by the authors of the SH2E project. [<https://sh2e.eu/>]

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This evaluation will review the different steps that the source follows to obtain their datasets, assigning different weights to the identified steps that the authors identify to produce LCA and LCC data. The evaluation weights are defined by the SH2E project in the following table:

Table 1. Evaluation of source transparency

Step	Evaluation			
	5 reviewed	4 transparent	3 reviewed	1 not reviewed not transparent or unknown
Raw data reviewed?	5 reviewed	1 not reviewed		
Unit process creation via transparent procedures that are reviewed?	5 reviewed and transparent	4 transparent	3 reviewed	1 not reviewed not transparent or unknown
Method-agnostic datasets reviewed?	5 reviewed	1 not reviewed		
Method-specific dataset creation via transparent procedures that are reviewed?	5 reviewed and transparent	4 transparent	3 reviewed	1 not reviewed not transparent or unknown
Dataset aggregation via transparent procedures that are reviewed?	5 reviewed and transparent	4 transparent	3 reviewed	1 not reviewed not transparent or unknown
Dataset connection via transparent procedures that are reviewed?	5 reviewed and transparent	4 transparent	3 reviewed	1 not reviewed not transparent or unknown

To evaluate the transparency of the data source, the following formula must be applied:

$$S_{tot} = \sqrt[n]{\prod_i S_i}$$

Where S_{tot} is the total score and s_i is the weight assigned to each of the 6 steps.

The values of S_{tot} can range from 1 to 5, and for the sources used in SINGLE this value **must be higher than 4**, so only the most reputable, transparent and reliable sources must be used.

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5. Data documentation

Documenting correctly the different datasets is vital to ensure that the data is correctly classified. All documents presented in the study (results, data, methods) must be transparent and detailed enough for the reader to comprehend the LCA and LCC. The ILCD Handbook describes the aspects that must be covered in order to ensure that the used datasets are documented correctly:

“Documentation captures several issues: the extent and detail of the documentation as key requirement to support transparency and to ensure that the results can be reproduced. At the same time the documentation is important for the LCA practitioner to know what the data set inventory actually represents, and whether it is the appropriate data for his/her systems. The form (report, data set) and format (ILCD reference format, ILCD report template etc) completes the documentation information, making sure that the documented information can be electronically exchanged without loss of information, etc.”

Correctly documenting a dataset will also aid significantly in the data quality review, simplifying the work of the reviewer and streamlining the process. To do so, all the characteristics and parameters that define the dataset must be stipulated in a standardized manner. The ILCD Handbook provides a template to classify all the different datasets and aid in the identification of the indicator value. The SINGLE project will follow a similar approach, using a variation of the template provided in the “Documentation of LCA datasets” adapted to the different data required for the models.

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6. Data quality evaluation

6.1 Introduction

LCA and LCC models will use data to assess the life cycle of the technology studied in the SINGLE project. The collected data that was previously described will have a direct influence on the results provided by these models. Although the project will produce relevant amounts of data, thanks to the pilot plant that will be built, it is common, and necessary, to extract data from public / generic databases to complete the LCA and LCC models. To ensure the results obtained from these models present a reliable picture of the life cycle of the technology, the accuracy and overall quality of the data used as input must be thoroughly reviewed.

In ISO 14044 chapter 4.2.3.6 a set of aspects regarding data quality are listed: representativeness, uncertainty / precision and methodological consistency, data sources used, and reproducibility. For the life cycle assessments performed in SINGLE to be reliable, all the data used will have to be reviewed following the different aspects listed within ISO 14044.

As described in the ILCD Handbook for LCA, data quality is addressed in two different, but complementary, approaches.

The first one is based on a set of indicators that allows the classification of the different datasets based on the overall quality of the data contained within them:

- Technological representativeness
- Geographical representativeness
- Time-related representativeness
- Completeness
- Precision / uncertainty
- Methodological appropriateness and consistency

The second one introduces aspects that complement the previously described data quality assessment, providing information regarding the obtainment of the set and its review and processing/nomenclature.

So, all datasets used in the SINGLE project will have to be accompanied by a set of information and procedures aimed at ensuring that all used datasets meet the required quality levels in the following 4 categories:

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- Overall data quality (Classification)
- Documentation
- Review
- Nomenclature

6.2 Overall data quality

6.2.1 Data quality indicators

Now a brief description of the different indicators that will be used to classify the overall quality of the datasets used in SINGLE will be provided, redacting in quotes the description given by the ILCD Handbook. For a more in-depth description, each indicator chapter is referenced.

Technological representativeness (Chapter 6.8.2)

“The technological representativeness of a process or system identifies how well the inventory data represents it regarding its true technological or technical characteristics that are documented in the descriptive information of the data set or report.”

This indicator rates the similarity between both the process and the products on which the dataset is based and the process and products in SINGLE. As an example, for the process, different approaches can be taken to produce hydrogen from ammonia, and the produced hydrogen can have different characteristics depending on the use (humidity, etc.).

The main objective of using this indicator is to assess if the technological background of the reviewed dataset is similar, or compatible, enough for the data contained in it to be adequate for the life cycle models.

Geographical representativeness (Chapter 6.8.3)

“The geographical representativeness of a process or system identifies how well the inventory data represents it regarding the location (e.g. market, site(s), region, country, etc.) that is documented in the descriptive information of the data set or report and where it is operated, produced, or consumed.”

This indicator rates the similarity between the geographical characteristics of where the data of the used dataset was recorded and the location of the case studies that will be evaluated in SINGLE. This helps assessing if the geographical and

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socioeconomic characteristics of the compared locations are similar enough to enable the models to give accurate outputs.

Time-related representativeness (Chapter 6.8.4)

"Degree to which the data set reflects the true population of interest regarding time/age of the data, including for included background data sets, if any."

Technology evolves over time, so datasets must be evaluated in this regard. Data obtained 5 years ago may be outdated due to a change in technology or in a variation of the socioeconomic characteristics. As you can see, this indicator can be related to the ones described previously.

As an example, a technology breakthrough can impact processes, rendering datasets previously obtained outdated and inaccurate. The socioeconomic situation of a region can drastically change overtime, leading to old datasets not being able to correctly represent the current situation of the region. For these reasons, it is vital that datasets are evaluated in their time representativeness, avoiding model outputs that are based on outdated scenarios that do not reflect the current state of the art of the technologies and value chains.

Completeness (Chapter 6.6.3)

"Share of (elementary) flows that are quantitatively included in the inventory. Note that for product and waste flows this needs to be judged on a system's level."

This indicator evaluates the relevancy of the flows and processes included in the dataset. As an example, a dataset would have high completeness if the data were obtained considering different sites of production during a long enough timeframe to provide clear data without fluctuations.

In the opposite case, a dataset will have low completeness if the dataset consists of a small number of data points taken in a short time frame, leading to the possibility of introducing inaccurate data to the model, and consequently obtaining inaccurate results.

Precision / uncertainty (Chapter 6.9.2)

"Measure of the variability of the data values for each data expressed (e.g. low variance = high precision). Note that for product and waste flows this needs to be judged on a system's level."

This indicator evaluates the variance of the data contained within the dataset that needs to be evaluated.

Methodological appropriateness and consistency (Chapter 6.5.4)

"The applied LCI methods and methodological choices (e.g. allocation, substitution, etc.) are in line with the goal and scope of the data set, especially its intended applications and decision support context. The methods also have been consistently applied across all data including for included processes, if any."

This indicator evaluates the methodology that has been followed to obtain the dataset.

Reliability of source

For most externally obtained datasets it will be difficult to judge the two last indicators, precision and methodological appropriateness. These will be substituted by an indicator that will evaluate the reliability of the source. This approach is made following the guidelines from SH2E.

This indicator will evaluate the source of the dataset, enduring that data obtained internally or from reputable databases has preference. As for data points that have a big impact on the results of the model, it will be important to discard unreliable sources to prevent inaccurate results. As an example, the highest value of the indicator will be assigned to the data obtained within SINGLE, from the pilot plant or other experimental measurements made by one of the partners. The lower qualifications will be given to data of unknown origin.

Summary

As a summary, the Overall Data Quality Indicators that must be evaluated for each dataset used in the models developed in SINGLE are:

- Technologic representativeness
- Geographical representativeness
- Time representativeness
- Completeness
- Reliability

6.2.2 Indicator Classification

Once the quality indicators have been defined, the next step is to give a definition of the different levels and the ratings assigned to each one. Following the ILCD Handbook, 5 quality levels for each indicator will be defined:

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Very good (Rating 1)

"Meets the criterion to a very high degree, having or no relevant need for improvement. This is to be judged in view of the criterion's contribution to the data set's potential overall impact, and in comparison to a hypothetical ideal data quality."

Good (Rating 2)

"Meets the criterion to a high degree, having little yet significant need for improvement. This is to be judged in view of the criterion's contribution to the data set's potential overall impact, and in comparison to a hypothetical ideal data quality."

Fair (Rating 3)

"Meets the criterion to a still sufficient degree, while having the need for improvement. This is to be judged in view of the criterion's contribution to the data set's potential overall impact, and in comparison to a hypothetical ideal data quality. "

Poor (Rating 4)

"Does not meet the criterion to a sufficient degree, having the need for relevant improvement. This is to be judged in view of the criterion's contribution to the data set's potential overall impact, and in comparison to a hypothetical ideal data quality."

Very poor (Rating 5)

"Does not at all meet the criterion, having the need for very substantial improvement. This is to be judged in view of the criterion's contribution to the data set's potential overall impact, and in comparison to a hypothetical ideal data quality."

6.2.3 Overall Data Quality Classification

To assess the overall data quality of a given dataset, the ratings of the different indicators will be summed up and averaged, counting the weakest quality level 5 times as described in the ILCD Handbook. The following formula must be used to calculate the overall quality:

$$DQR = \frac{TeR + GR + TiR + C + R + Wr * 4}{i + 4}$$

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Where:

- DQR: Data quality rating
- TeR: Technology representativeness
- GR: Geographical representativeness
- TiR: Time representativeness
- C: Completeness
- R: Reliability
- Wr: Weakest rating
- i: Number of data quality indicators

Once the data quality rating has been obtained, an **Overall Data Quality Level** will be assigned:

Table 2. Overall Data Quality Level

Data Quality Rating	Overall Data Quality
≤ 1.6	High quality
>1.6 to ≤ 3	Basic quality
>3 to ≤ 4	Data estimate
>4	Discarded data

6.2.4 Pedigree table for data quality assessment

To better streamline the process of the overall data classification, the SH2E approach of creating a pedigree table is followed. The following table must be used to classify the datasets used in the different models that will be created throughout SINGLE.

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Table 3. Pedigree table for data quality assessment in SINGLE.

Rating =	1	2	3	4	5
Technology representativeness	Data from processes, materials and costs obtained internally	Data from processes, materials and costs of same technology obtained from a source outside SINGLE	Data from processes, materials, and costs of different technology	Data from related processes, materials, or costs	Data from related processes, materials, or costs on laboratory scale
Geographical representativeness	Data from area under study	Average data from larger region in which the study area is included	Data from area with similar socioeconomic and production characteristics	Data from area with slightly similar socioeconomic and production characteristics	Data from unknown or significantly different socioeconomic and production characteristics
Time representativeness	Less than 1 year of difference	Less than 2 years of difference	Less than 4 years of difference	Less than 8 years of difference	Age of data unknown or more than 8 years of difference
Completeness	Data from enough sites over an adequate period	Data from a small number of sites over an adequate period	Data from enough sites over a short period	Incomplete data from enough sites over an adequate period	Data from a small number of sites over a short period or completeness unknown
Reliability	Verified data based on measurements	Verified data based on assumptions or non-verified data based on measurements	Non-verified data partly based on assumptions	Qualified estimate	Non-qualified estimate or unknown origin

6.3 Reviewing process

All of the previous methodology will be implemented in a standardized manner to ensure that the process is transparent. To do so, a reviewing form, similar to the documentation one described in previous chapters, will be filled for each new set of data that is both relevant to the researcher and has also passed the source screening test (in the case of secondary sources).

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Each dataset must be reviewed by a competent individual. To choose said individual, the ILCD Handbook includes a document named “Reviewer qualification for Life Cycle Inventory data sets” which details the process for choosing an adequate professional to carry out the dataset's reviews.

Once the group of professionals has been selected, each dataset will be accompanied by a review which will encompass all of the subjects that are included in data quality. Once the reviewing process has been finalized, the reviewer will assess the validity of the dataset, describing the instances where is adequate to use, and discarding it if necessary. The reviewing process will ensure that only good and reliable data is fed into the models.

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7. Nomenclature

Once all the previous steps have been fulfilled, ensuring that the dataset terminology, units, and parameters are compatible with both the models and other datasets of the project will be the final step of the data collection methodology.

To ensure a clear treatment of the different datasets, proper nomenclature guidelines must be followed. As described in the ILCD Handbook: “Nomenclature is an issue that predominantly relates to the used naming and structuring of elementary flows and other named elements. This ensure that different practitioners can at all consistently work with the data and that the LCI data can be correctly linked with the LCIA factors. Correct and consistent use of LCA terminology is a second component under “Nomenclature”.

The ILCD Handbook provides a document named “Nomenclature and other conventions” that all SINGLE partners must follow when processing the datasets that will be used.

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8. Conclusions

Ensuring that the data used in the various SINGLE models has good quality and comes from a reliable source is vital for the validation of results. Following the process described in this document will ensure that the quality of the data meets the transparency and quality requirements to pass a reviewing process and satisfies the expected standards for the types of studies previously described. Following the data quality evaluation process will ensure that the models have solid foundations, and, if they are reviewed, the datasets source and quality will be traceable.

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